

Interview - HealthUser experience team, Health Data UK

Authors:

Poppy Townsend

Affiliations:

NERC Environmental Data Service, Science and Technology Facilities Council

About this work

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. The work was undertaken by members of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

This is a summary report to provide supporting information to the overarching report - User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115280>)

Summary

This document describes an interview undertaken as part of the context setting work. You can find a synthesis of all other interviews here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15102198>

Interview: HealthUser experience team, Health Data UK

Meeting date: 04/03/2025

Health Data UK (HDR UK) is the national institute for health data science. Our mission is to unite the UK's health data to enable discoveries that improve people's lives.

We spoke to the user experience team of two. They have a range of experience, one had a UX design background and previously worked in the private sector, the other was focused in public engagement and medical communication, and has worked on projects in VR/interactive animation. They were both new to the user experience team at HDR UK within the last few months.

HDR :

300 employees in total

70 in technology, rest more political/administrative

2 in UX team

UX team time is assigned by line managers in various projects, often based on funding

Biggest challenges:

- Delivery focus rather than user focus - focus on deadlines, unable/reluctant to involve many users on short time scales
- Fear of sharing incomplete work with users, A lot of science work is based on trust - reluctance to share unfinished work that is not 'perfect'.
 - Shifting this mindset to trust built by transparency and making users feel included in process
- High turnover of designers on projects - need to spend time unpicking the work from the start, slow approval process for change

- Funding timescales - not enough time to gather user feedback
- We are not likely to get designated designers - need to upskill colleagues in user focused design where the norm is delivery focus

Toolkit and future work:

- Keen to be involved, beneficial to develop community of practice and share across domains
- Broadening toolkit to wider audience, domain specific case studies